

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE

Report on barriers hampering cooperation on R & I

Deliverable 1.6

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EELISA innoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive Summary

This document has been prepared for the fulfilment of delivery D1.6. "Report on barriers hampering cooperation on R & I" within the work package WP1 – 'Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination of the project EELISA Innovation and Common Research Strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA innoCORE).

We provide an analysis of the barriers hampering cooperation on R&I by considering the Institutional Transformation Modules (ITMs) of EELISA innoCORE Grant Agreement and 11 strategic objectives (OB) linked to the ITMs as well.

Various exercises have been conducted during some meetings attended by EELISA partners to identify the barriers hampering cooperation in R & I and measures to overcome these barriers. Additionally, a questionnaire was designed to collect data on "Barriers hampering cooperation on R&I" among EELISA partners, and the main actions to overcome these barriers', and distributed to EELISA Community leaders and EELISA innoCORE project WP representatives. The inputs below were used for preparing the report (see Annex I):

- (1) Pisa & Madrid innoCORE meetings Miro boards
- (2) EELISA / innoCORE project team questionnaire
- (3) EELISA community questionnaire
- (4) D1.3 Policy Brief
- (5) D2.2 Summary of I. Symposia with Representatives of R&I Structures

Data from multiple sources in this report show that "institutional" barriers should be addressed at consortium level to fully exploit the potential of EELISA partners for effective collaboration in the R&I field, while a combination of "institutional" and "outreach" measures are to be prioritized within the EELISA European University to support joint research and innovation initiatives.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(Alphabetical order)

CA: Consortium Agreement: The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency)

EELISA innoCORE Cluster: EELISA innoCORE Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solving the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Community: The EELISA communities are mission-driven collaboration and working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges

EIPO: European and International Project Office.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

HE: Horizon Europe.

HEIs: Higher Education Institutions

ITM: Institutional Transformation Modules

OB: Strategic Objectives defined in EELISA innoCORE Grant agreement

OS: Open Science

R & I. Research and Innovation

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1. Methodology

EELISA innoCORE partners analyzed the barriers and challenges hampering R&I collaboration at various meetings so far. This deliverable reports the outcomes from brainstorming sessions held by the representatives of R&I structures of the EELISA innoCORE partners, who held hands-on workshops in Pisa in April 2022 and Madrid in September 2022 (see Figure 1) respectively. First, EELISA partners analyzed barriers, challenges and risks regarding the progress in relation to eleven strategic objectives (OBs) as described in the GA (section 1.1 in the GA and Table 2 below) during a dedicated onsite strategic meeting in Pisa in April 2022. Later, in Madrid a meeting was fully dedicated to analyze the progress, barriers and challenges against institutional transformation modules (ITMs) using MIRO as a brainstorming tool (see Annex I and II for details). Since the same Miro board was used for these consecutive sessions, feedback from R&I representatives were based on both OBs and ITMs in a holistic manner to arrive at conclusions (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The exercises on Miro Board in Pisa and Madrid meetings

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Additionally, a questionnaire targeting EELISA community members and the EELISA and EELISA-innoCORE project team members were designed (see Annex III). The instrument included two open-ended questions:

- 1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?
- 2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

Qualitative content analysis was conducted to analyze data from Miro boards. Textual materials relating barriers were coded by the authors to identify themes following a coding process. Consensus was sought between the authors in the inductive coding process. Data from questionnaires survey, including the responses of 11 EELISA and EELISA-innoCORE project team members and EELISA Community members (<https://community.eelisa.eu>) were classified according to the inductive categories including "Institutional Factors", "Outreach", "Funding", "External Stakeholder Engagement" and "Inter-Alliance Cooperation". They were organized according to the top-down categories of 7 ITM modules as listed in Table 1. Eleven strategic objectives of EELISA innoCORE were also considered when reporting outcomes from the analyses (see Table 2 and Figure 2). Main actions and measures to overcome the barriers were classified with a similar method. Additionally, the innoCORE deliverables entitled "D1.3 Policy brief" and "D2.2 Summary- of I. Symposia with Representatives of R&I Structures" were used as inputs for analyses. All inputs for analyses were numbered and indicated in Table 3 and Table 4.

- (1) Pisa & Madrid innoCORE meetings Miro boards (Annex I & Annex II)
- (2) EELISA / innoCORE Project team questionnaire (Annex III)
- (3) EELISA Community questionnaire (Annex III)
- (4) D1.3 Policy Brief (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7525636>)
- (5) D2.2 Summary of I. Symposia with Representatives of R&I Structures (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574978>)

Table 1. List of Institutional Transformation Modules of EELISA innoCORE according to Grant Agreement

ITM-1: Developing a common research and innovation agenda and convergence action plan and its implementation, in synergy with education strategies and regional engagement
ITM-2: Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance
ITM-3: Sharing research infrastructures and other resources
ITM-4: Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, esp. academia-business cooperation; with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market
ITM-5: Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science (OS) practices
ITM-6: Involving and engaging citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation
ITM-7: Exploring joint structures across the European Universities on technical activities common to all European Universities

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Table 2. List of Strategic Objectives (OBs) of EELISA innoCORE according to Grant Agreement

OB1	Achieve a common research and innovation strategy adopting a bottom-up approach.
OB2	Reinforce our policies on Open Science through new and innovative mechanisms and tools and new ways in which change can be successfully embedded in our universities
OB3	Create multi-labs
OB4	Enable joint research
OB5	Support joint research
OB6	Optimize outreach of EELISA innoCORE
OB7	Increase the internationalization of our R&I structures within and beyond Europe
OB8	Be a source of inspiration
OB9	Achieve an effective and efficient collaboration
OB10	Strengthen the link between European Research Area and European Education Area
OB11	Contribute to the future Commission policy initiatives in Research and Innovation

Figure 2. Linkage between ITM s and Strategic Objectives (Source: H2020 Periodic Technical Report Part B_RP1_final.pdf)

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2. Findings

Following a content analysis, barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimension of EELISA European University were categorized under the headings of "Institutional", "Outreach", "Funding", "External stakeholder engagement" and "Inter-alliance cooperation". From a general perspective, Table 2 shows that "institutional" factors represent the most significant barriers to the cooperation of EELISA partners in the R&I field.

Under ITM module 1 (*Developing a common research and innovation agenda and convergence action plan and its implementation, in synergy with education strategies and regional engagement*), data from respondents show that mainly the "institutional barrier" hampers the cooperation between EELISA partners in relation to strategic objectives including OB1 (achieve a common research and innovation strategy adopting a bottom-up approach), OB2 (support joint research), and OB3 (optimize outreach of EELISA innoCORE).

Under ITM module 2 (*Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance*), data from respondents show that the "institutional", "outreach" and "funding" barriers hamper the cooperation between EELISA partners in relation to strategic objectives including OB5 (support joint research), OB6 (optimize outreach of EELISA innoCORE), OB7 (increase the internationalization of our R&I structures within and beyond Europe), and OB9 (achieve an effective and efficient collaboration).

Under ITM module 3 (*sharing research infrastructures and other resources*), data from respondents show that the "institutional" and "funding" barriers hamper the cooperation between EELISA partners in relation to strategic objectives including OB3 (create multi-labs) and OB4 (enable joint research).

Under ITM module 4 (*Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, esp. Academia-business cooperation; with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market*); data from respondents show that "External stakeholder engagement" and "funding" barriers hamper the cooperation between EELISA partners in relation to strategic objectives including OB6 (Optimize outreach of EELISA innoCORE).

Under ITM module 5 (*Mainstreaming of comprehensive Open Science practices*), data from respondents show that mainly the "institutional" barrier hampers the cooperation between EELISA partners in relation to the strategic objective OB2 (support joint research).

Under ITM module 6 (*Involving and engaging citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation*), data from respondents show that mainly the "outreach" barriers hamper the cooperation between EELISA partners in relation to strategic objectives including OB6 (optimize outreach of EELISA innoCORE) and OB 8 (be a source of inspiration).

Under ITM module 7 (*Inter-alliance cooperation*) data from respondents show that mainly the "Inter-alliance cooperation" barriers hamper the cooperation between EELISA partners in relation to strategic objectives including OB8 (Be a source of inspiration), OB10 (strengthen the link between European Research Area and European Education Area) and OB11 (contribute to the future Commission policy initiative in Research and Innovation).

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Table 3. Barriers hampering cooperation on R & I regarding ITMs

ITM No	Category	Barriers	Objectives	Sources	
1	Institutional factors	“The lack of common protocols/guidelines”	OB1	(1)	
		“The presence of so many tools (<i>open calls, networking platform, catalogue of infrastructures</i>) made available for R&I that often proceed in parallel and concurrently”	OB5	(1) (2)	
			OB6		
			“Difficulties to find common topics of interest for building joint research proposals”		(1)
			“The lack of as well as different practices between universities create a barrier”		(2)
“Differences between the governance, autonomy and capacity of project offices across EELISA partners”	(5)				
ITM No	Category	Barriers	Objectives	Sources	
2	Outreach	“Still weak linkage between EELISA Communities and innoCORE clusters - Reaching and persuading researchers to form communities and propose projects/building proto-clusters (clusters are under formation)”	OB5 OB6 OB7 OB9	(1) (2) (5)	

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		<p>“Lack of involvement / loss of interest of individual researchers and research groups which already have well-established networks and collaborations in the scientific community -lack of motivation for Community membership which is seen as an additional work with limited added value”.</p>		(2) (1) (4)
		<p>“Difficulty to onboard new researchers, academics and innovators and keep their scientific interest at the heart of the project. Furthermore; Lack of knowledge and difficulties in getting to know what other colleagues are doing”</p>		(2)
	Funding	<p>“Lack of sustainable funding systems for joint research initiatives”</p>		(1) (3)
	Institutional factors	<p>“Limited time and heavy workload of academic staff dealing with research and teaching responsibilities”</p>		(3) (4) (5)
ITM No	Category	Barriers	Objectives	Sources
3	Institutional factors	<p>“Lack of interoperability of EELISA IT platforms and solutions different levels of digitalisation and digitation of resources among EELISA partners in terms of both “already existing as well as newly created IT platforms”</p>	OB3 OB4	(1) (4)
		<p>“Difficulty to share infrastructure without a legal framework (alignment of local procedures, avoiding extra bureaucracy) / The lack of common protocols/guidelines (e.g., procedures for multi-lab)”</p>		(1)

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		“Lack of an appealing presentation of the shared research infrastructures for researchers / Difficulty to keep infrastructure catalogue updated”		(1) (4)
		“Unwillingness of researchers to share facilities”		(1)
	Funding	“Inadequate level of resources to support mobility and infrastructure sharing, and to put in place appealing IT solutions. Uncertainties regarding the long-term financial sustainability of the tools created”		(1)
ITM No	Category	Barriers	Objectives	Sources
4	External stakeholder engagement	“Getting investors and industry onboard”	OB6	(1)
		“Lack of an effective external collaboration model/strategy”		(3)
		“Need to find compromises and strike a balance with already existing initiatives and agreements at each partner-level. EELISA partners have collaborations with other universities and research centres, they participate in associations and networks and have agreements with big industry players etc. at all levels (regional, national, European and international). The construction of EELISA European University, although being strategic for our partners, needs to coexist with other initiatives that cannot be neglected”		(4)

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	Funding	“Lack of long-term funding of activities (e.g., test space for prototypes)”		(1)
ITM No	Category	Barriers	Objectives	Sources
5	Institutional factors	“Tension between existing research assessment practices and the new OS paradigm”	OB2	(1)
		“Low awareness among researchers on OS practices in different EELISA institutions”		(1)
		“Insufficient dedicated staff to deal with OS”		(1)
ITM No	Category	Barriers	Objectives	Sources
6	Outreach	“Challenges relating the involvement of non-academic staff (public authorities, large public)”	OB6 OB8	(1)
		“Difficulties in putting together appealing public events and attracting public, due to the high number of events going on”		
ITM No	Category	Barriers	Objectives	Sources
7	Inter-alliance cooperation	“Need of a reinforced cooperation with alliances from the first wave”	OB8	(1)

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		“Political events and force majeure circumstances”	OB10 OB11	(2)
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Table 4 reports the recommendations for overcoming barriers to the cooperation of EELISA partners in the R&I field, in relation to Table 3. Data from respondents show that "institutional" and "outreach" measures are perceived as critical by respondents to address the barriers to hampering cooperation.

Creating networking opportunities for researchers through appropriate platforms and tools; the use of joint potential of Project Offices; identification of institutional differences; the post-analysis of R&I-related initiatives across the Alliance; the development of common rules and procedures to access infrastructures and laboratories; better alignment with EELISA Communities, external stakeholders and societal actors and the promotion of OS practices and tools are amongst the “institution-level” measures for overcoming barriers.

According to respondents, the development of a strategy for managing external stakeholders; a stronger connection between EELISA Communities and EELISA innoCORE Clusters; building a narrative on the added value from the European University; increasing the visibility of researchers and research infrastructures; supporting early-career researchers; and the promotion of OS practices within the EELISA ecosystem are amongst the "outreach" measures to address challenges in the R&I field.

Table 4. Recommendations to overcome the barriers regarding ITMs

ITM No	Category	Recommendations	Sources
1	Institutional factors	“More integrated and holistic/complementary use of networking spaces, events, platforms and tools developed so far within the consortium”	(1) (2) (4)
		“Reinforcing the connection among EELISA European Project Offices and TTOs (Technology Transfer Officers) to connect internal services of partners beyond innoCORE /EELISA core team (e.g., a fully dedicated staff), particularly to enable joint research”	(1) (3)
		“Creation of a task force to identify the institutional differences between partners, in particular the legal ones, to select good practices”	(2)

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	Outreach	“Development of a holistic outreach and management strategy for external stakeholders, which encompasses all the dimensions of the Alliance (education, research & innovation, entrepreneurship)”.	(1) (4)
	Funding	“Extend and reinforce the use of open calls (e.g., innoCORE connect call for workshops, EELISA Prototype Contest) to facilitate networking for joint research and innovation projects”	(1) (4)
ITM No	Category	Recommendations	Sources
2	Outreach	“Development of a strategic vision and narrative for a stronger connection between EELISA Communities and innoCORE Clusters through embedding R&I component into Community-based activities”	(1) (2)
		“Building a narrative on EELISA’s added value and alliance-level collaboration to motivate researchers to work together”	(1)
		“Increasing the visibility of researchers and research infrastructures through attractive platforms and tools (e.g., web sites, catalogue of infrastructures, and others)”	(1)
		“Adoption of a comprehensive approach for joint event and calls to address diverse motivation of EELISA members in the education, research, entrepreneurship & innovation fields”	(3)
	Institutional factors	“Post-analysis of R&I-related initiatives, including the open calls launched, to identify lessons learned and improve measures for increasing the involvement of researchers and innovators”.	(4)

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		“Developing governance structures and contact points in each institution aimed at bringing EELISA European Project Offices and TTOs together to connect internal services of partners beyond innoCORE /EELISA core team, particularly to enable joint research”	(1) (2) (5)
	Funding	“Extend and reinforce the use of open calls (e.g., I innoCORE connect call for workshops, EELISA Prototype Contest) to facilitate networking for joint research and innovation projects”	(1) (3)
ITM No	Category	Recommendations	Sources
3	Institutional factors	“Formalisation of access to infrastructures and laboratories through the development of shared principles and procedures. Deepening analyses and work performed under WP4, particularly D4.2 Agreement on the main consensual rules of access to open facilities)”	(1)
		“Better alignment with other R&I initiatives at different levels (e.g., national, regional, inter-university, inter-alliance, etc)”	(1)
		“Barriers to the interoperability of EELISA IT platforms should be addressed by considering the local, regional or national aspects and differences, and be supported by regional and national authorities with decentralised budgets, including European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) or NextGenerationEU”	(4)
	Outreach	“Increasing the visibility of research infrastructures through attractive and tools”	(1)
ITM No	Category	Recommendations	Sources
4	Institutional factors	“Alignment of R&I dimension of EELISA with the existing commitments and agreements of the partnering institutions with external actors”	(2)
		“Development of an efficient external stakeholder reach out and management strategy for EELISA portfolio of projects”	(1) (2) (4)
ITM No	Category	Recommendations	Sources
5	Outreach	“Reinforcing dissemination of EELISA innoCORE outputs, especially among the early-career researchers”	(1) (2)
		“Active use of OS Training Hub (under development)”	(1)

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		“Developing and fully exploiting the network of EELISA OS Ambassadors (under development)”	(1)
	Institutional factors	“Rewarding excellence in Open Science (OS) according with new Agreement on RRA”	(1) (2)
ITM No	Category	Recommendations	Sources
6	Institutional factors	“Better coordination of EELISA portfolio of projects for involving and engaging citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in R&I”	(1) (4)
	Outreach	“Enhancing the dissemination of communication channels / Developing common dissemination and communication strategies”	(2)
	External stakeholder engagement	“Development of an efficient external stakeholder reach out and management strategy for EELISA portfolio of projects”	(1) (2) (4)
		“Use of R&I infrastructure of EELISA partners for better public engagement (e.g., EELISA Prototype Contest in cooperation with the JOSEPHS)”	(1)
ITM No	Category	Recommendations	Sources
7	Inter-alliance cooperation	“Face-to-face meetings with Alliances”	(1)
		“Reinforce participation in local and regional activities”	(1)

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3. Conclusion

The barriers hampering cooperation in the R&I field were analyzed according to Institutional Transformation Modules ITMs of EELISA innoCORE Grant Agreement and the relevant strategic objectives (OB).

Data from multiple sources show that "institutional" barriers such as the lack of common protocols/guidelines, the legislative differences between EELISA partners; the dissimilarities amongst the governance, autonomy and capacity of project offices, researchers with already existing heavy workloads and the lack of interoperability of EELISA IT platforms should have priority when addressing challenges relating collaboration in the R&I wing of the EELISA European University.

Analyses of data regarding recommendations to overcome barriers to R&I cooperation suggest that "institutional" and "outreach" measures are to be prioritized within the EELISA European University to support joint research and innovation initiatives. Stronger connection between EELISA Communities and innoCORE Clusters, developing a strategy for an efficient engagement with external stakeholders, promoting open science practices, and increasing the visibility of researchers and research infrastructures through attractive networking platforms and tools are amongst the measures to be taken.

Open calls facilitate the creation of strong connections between EELISA communities and innoCORE Clusters, however, their design remains a challenge. For future design of "Open Calls", especially in the second phase of the EELISA project; more effort should be paid to address the barriers or concerns below:

- Allocation of higher amount of budget for the calls.
- Unattractive budget compared to other calls.
- Heavy workload of researchers
- Researchers with already existing networks
- Differences in legislative and administrative frameworks and rules.
- Lack of knowledge and difficulties in getting to know what other colleagues are doing.
- Difficulties in accessing peers

As part of the systemic analyses of challenges and barriers, EELISA partners are already working on some of these barriers identified. As a matter of example, WP4 is working on an IT platform for the catalogue of infrastructures (recommendation "Increasing the visibility of researchers and research infrastructures through attractive platforms and tools"). WP3 is working on setting up the network of OS Ambassadors. During their meeting on 5 May, ACRI (Advisory Council for Research and Innovation) issued some recommendations for the improvement of the EELISA Connect call for workshops, which will also be further evaluated. WP1 is actively participating and sharing knowledge gathered in FOREU meetings.

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Annex I – Data from Pisa innoCORE meetings Miro boards

OBJECTIVE (AS PER GA)	Description (as per GA)	Tangible progress (as per GA)	Current tangible progress	Barriers and challenges	Risks	Strategic orientations to meet the objective
Achieve a common research and innovation strategy adopting a bottom-up approach	EELISA Communities are challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia collaborate to face societal challenges. Our researchers, research groups, innovators and start-ups will collaborate to address the scientific and technological needs of these communities through joint research projects and new R&I structures.	Engagement of a considerable number of our researchers and innovators in the challenge facing process occurring within EELISA Communities (participating in joint R&I actions)	D2.1 mapping of capacities in the labs Development of shared protocol D2.1 mapping of capacities, the currently ready priority research areas starting from existing competences	High online and collaboration tools Institutional barriers of access Need of shared digital spaces Need of shared digital spaces	Not identifying future directions clearly Institutional risks due to pandemic Researcher mobility not being clearly defined Researcher mobility not being clearly defined	How should we use D2.1? Developing a training for the connection of communities and clusters Local initiatives & National Research events
Create multi-labs	We will empower our researchers by giving them the opportunity to use the facilities and equipment currently owned by the partners in their laboratories. This will be achieved with the creation of a simple booking system connecting facilities and equipment. Thanks to sharing facilities, or the set-up of new facilities or ultimately the creation of joint facilities, EELISA labs will be connected. Those networks will be called "Multi Labs".	Number and value of resources included in the portfolio: Search, find and book tools	First survey of the existing infrastructure completed In progress: understanding every state on open labs Definition of shared information about existing facilities Sharing understanding of opportunities	Availability of facilities and equipment If Platforms engagement and need for IT resources Not enough resources to be allocated Mapping of mobility of researchers on lab networks	Mapping of mobility of researchers on lab networks Mapping of mobility of researchers on lab networks Mapping of mobility of researchers on lab networks	Applying to funds for capacity building Applying to funds for capacity building
Enable joint research	Our Researchers will find not only the opportunity to interact with non-academic actors in the communities, but also to work collaboratively with other colleagues and to organise stable R&I structures with shared long-term visions.	Number of R&I structures. Number of R&I joint initiatives	Survey of existing joint research projects started	Motivation? Limited availability of funding Other partners' responsibilities for structures Coordination with internal governance of research	Loss of participant disinterest Disagreements on how to use the funds for open labs Not all domains were identified or aligned with EELISA Responsibility for legal (common) topics	Active search of projects Active search of researchers Communication pilot event Evaluation "openness" External, focused Diffusion
Support joint research	R&I structures created to face a specific challenge are expected to grow and stay, facing new social challenges identified by other EELISA communities. We will support these structures through idea generation workshop, targeted seed funding and proposal support in order to bring them into excellence.	Number of submitted joint projects.	Collection of research projects (management) started	Other partners' responsibilities for structures Coordination with internal governance of research Points needed for the deliverable have already been assessed and discussed. But these materials are only based on the individual institutional practices and no integration has yet taken place. No initiatives have been proposed to really do something together. We have to launch this barrier. Motivation, opportunities should be clear Business models? P's sharing and explanation	Not enough resources to be allocated Responsibility for legal (common) topics	How should we use and implement open labs? Applying to funds for capacity building
Optimize outreach of EELISA innoCORE	Specific actions to strengthen the links between R&I structures, industries and society created in communities.	PhD thesis funded by industry and co-advised by researchers. Industrial Chairs. Start-ups Business incubators Publicly visible events and media contributions.	EELISA Innovation Talks will start this summer Emergence of tangible opportunities to disseminate Points needed for the deliverable have already been assessed and discussed. But these materials are only based on the individual institutional practices and no integration has yet taken place. No initiatives have been proposed to really do something together. We have to launch this barrier. Motivation, opportunities should be clear Business models? P's sharing and explanation	Not enough resources to be allocated Responsibility for legal (common) topics	Industry chair with multinational company Arbitrage in the alliance members an eager dissemination for cooperation	
Reinforce our policies on Open Science	Mapping and benchmarking our current practices on Open Science, identifying a common set of good practice needs to be applied in OS institutional policies improvement together with detailed OS institutional implementation / Action Plans as well as the initial implementation of the respective action plans.	A common framework of OS practices which will allow to continue sharing strategies on policy implementation, creating shared training modules, open data tools and services, incentive and reward mechanism, identifying opportunities for shared infrastructure for real challenges in our universities.	First DIMP of initiatives project which will be updated First DIMP of initiatives project which will be updated First DIMP of initiatives project which will be updated	external publications constraints Lower levels of awareness related to OS Levels of awareness different between institutions which can provide viable R&I collaboration Gaps between institutions	Levels of awareness different between institutions which can provide viable R&I collaboration Gaps between institutions	
Increase the internationalisation of our R&I structures within and beyond Europe	The creation of groups with participants from several institutions across Europe (7 countries and 3 regions)	Creation of international sustainable R&I structures				
Be a source of inspiration	EELISA innoCORE aims to be a successful cooperation and governance alignment model in the knowledge society (education, research, service to society, including innovation). By opening our research and innovation for communities and citizens, we aim at inspiring not only scientific partners but also public debate.	Collaboration with other European Universities. Publicly visible events and media contributions link "EELISA Innovation Talks"	First infodays event on OS			A proper communication and dissemination plan should be developed
Achieve an effective and efficient collaboration	Analyse the cost-benefits of actions, with a particular focus on diversity across disciplines, institutions and regions as well as gender balance.	Quantification of costs and benefits of every action.		Involvement of partners staff and government which are directly involved in the projects		
Contribute to the future Commission policy initiatives in Research and Innovation/collaboration	Sharing the process and results with the European Commission (in particular, the results of cost-benefit analyses and the identification of barriers) and with the Member States in order to achieve successful models of cooperation between researchers, innovators, citizens and industry. Generated knowledge will have an impact on policy initiatives by the EC, e.g. as regards upcoming fields and technologies.					
Strengthen the link between European Research Area and European Education Area	This project pursues the long term vision of our alliance, the creation of a European University that is an important actor in both ERA and European Education Areas.	Creation of R&I structures with participants from several European higher education institutes.				

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Annex II – Data from Madrid innoCORE meetings Miro boards

Reflection exercise for the Madrid meetings on 22 & 23 September. We would like to ask you to please read progress report Y1 before completing the MIRO. [Here](#), Progress report Y1 has been elaborated by the coordinator with the aim of providing input and triggering debate for this exercise. The boxes "GA Description" and "Current tangible progress as per GA" is what the GA reads. That text is copied-pasted from the GA. We would like partners to evaluate actual progress (what we have done) and the challenges we have ahead, taking into

Institutional Transformation Module	GA Description (page 7)	Tangible progress as per GA (page 15)	Current tangible progress	Barriers, challenges, risks	To be done, work ahead	Main responsible WP
ITM1 - Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan	<p>Rather than proposing strategic research lines for our researchers and innovators (top-down approach), we will pave the way for a natural, bottom-up, convergence towards a shared strategy. In the strategy of our partners, researchers may already decide, together with students, faculty and staff what ELISA communities to plant and grow. We just facilitate the land to plant communities and resources to grow these organisms. Now, with ELISA innoCORE, our researchers and innovators will decide themselves the most effective way to address scientific or technological challenges that will feed communities and vice-versa. They will transform the R&D dimension of ELISA communities by organizing themselves to build joint research or innovation actions. Once they have done so, they may opt to create permanent R&I structures: research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, joint ventures, science parks that would conduct searching for new societal challenges and communities. We will make it possible the creation of these structures and will support them and to maximize their outreach.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Map of strategic areas of all the members, including innoCARE - Networking Platform - Portfolio of societal needs that require scientific or technical solutions 	<p>Map of strategic areas of all the members, including innoCARE</p> <p>Networking Platform</p> <p>Portfolio of societal needs that require scientific or technical solutions</p>	<p>Map of strategic areas of all the members, including innoCARE</p> <p>Networking Platform</p> <p>Portfolio of societal needs that require scientific or technical solutions</p>	<p>Map of strategic areas of all the members, including innoCARE</p> <p>Networking Platform</p> <p>Portfolio of societal needs that require scientific or technical solutions</p>	<p>Map of strategic areas of all the members, including innoCARE</p> <p>Networking Platform</p> <p>Portfolio of societal needs that require scientific or technical solutions</p>
ITM2 - Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance	<p>The mission of joint research projects and the creation of research structures in the context of ELISA communities will add value to our research actions, as they will be carried out with and for actors out of academia. Actions to facilitate the meeting ELISA Networking Platform and ELISA Connect will foster multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary and even crossdisciplinary. The necessary multidisciplinary nature of R&I structures in the context of ELISA Multi Lab will consequently increase mobility.</p> <p>Our Gender Equality Plan, the cost-benefit analyses and the award of gender equality awards will positively impact on the gender equality. We are particularly concerned on this aspect as our higher education institution mainly focus in engineering disciplines where traditionally men are more present than women.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of at least one R&I structure (cluster, startup, joint venture) per ELISA community, with members (individual researchers or innovators, research groups, tech companies) from at least 3 different countries per ELISA community. - Gender Equality Plan - RB Excellence award 	<p>Creation of at least one R&I structure (cluster, startup, joint venture) per ELISA community, with members (individual researchers or innovators, research groups, tech companies) from at least 3 different countries per ELISA community.</p> <p>Gender Equality Plan</p> <p>RB Excellence award</p>	<p>Creation of at least one R&I structure (cluster, startup, joint venture) per ELISA community, with members (individual researchers or innovators, research groups, tech companies) from at least 3 different countries per ELISA community.</p> <p>Gender Equality Plan</p> <p>RB Excellence award</p>	<p>Creation of at least one R&I structure (cluster, startup, joint venture) per ELISA community, with members (individual researchers or innovators, research groups, tech companies) from at least 3 different countries per ELISA community.</p> <p>Gender Equality Plan</p> <p>RB Excellence award</p>	<p>Creation of at least one R&I structure (cluster, startup, joint venture) per ELISA community, with members (individual researchers or innovators, research groups, tech companies) from at least 3 different countries per ELISA community.</p> <p>Gender Equality Plan</p> <p>RB Excellence award</p>
ITM3 - Sharing research infrastructures and other resources	<p>The creation of ELISA Multi Labs will be an unprecedented experience of collaboration between our institutions and facilities. The sharing of facilities will empower our researchers, under principles of safety, efficiency and equity while making our institutions more resilient.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Portfolio of open infrastructures and equipment - Common policy for the alliance on infrastructure and equipment sharing - Roadmap for new infrastructures building and guidelines 	<p>Portfolio of open infrastructures and equipment</p> <p>Common policy for the alliance on infrastructure and equipment sharing</p> <p>Roadmap for new infrastructures building and guidelines</p>	<p>Portfolio of open infrastructures and equipment</p> <p>Common policy for the alliance on infrastructure and equipment sharing</p> <p>Roadmap for new infrastructures building and guidelines</p>	<p>Portfolio of open infrastructures and equipment</p> <p>Common policy for the alliance on infrastructure and equipment sharing</p> <p>Roadmap for new infrastructures building and guidelines</p>	<p>Portfolio of open infrastructures and equipment</p> <p>Common policy for the alliance on infrastructure and equipment sharing</p> <p>Roadmap for new infrastructures building and guidelines</p>
ITM4 - Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market	<p>The members of ELISA have already established strong collaborations with civil societies, NGOs, hospitals, local governments and industries in their respective countries. They benefit from important industrial income in the framework of their higher education. Having training and R&I activities. The major added value of the present project will be fostering best practices between partners: gathering resources and tools of innovative technology transfer structures (technology transfer offices, incubators, innovation centres, etc.) within ELISA in order to be credible in the eyes of companies at international level and to internationalise ELISA transfer services. The creation of an infrastructure of business incubators across ELISA and funding for an ELISA wise start-up initiative are part of our project. In addition, we will set up an international network of joint academia/industry laboratories.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of PhD theses financed by industry and co-financed in the context of ELISA community. - Start-up initiatives - Number of industrial chairs and industry-university labs 	<p>Number of PhD theses financed by industry and co-financed in the context of ELISA community.</p> <p>Start-up initiatives</p> <p>Number of industrial chairs and industry-university labs</p>	<p>Number of PhD theses financed by industry and co-financed in the context of ELISA community.</p> <p>Start-up initiatives</p> <p>Number of industrial chairs and industry-university labs</p>	<p>Number of PhD theses financed by industry and co-financed in the context of ELISA community.</p> <p>Start-up initiatives</p> <p>Number of industrial chairs and industry-university labs</p>	<p>Number of PhD theses financed by industry and co-financed in the context of ELISA community.</p> <p>Start-up initiatives</p> <p>Number of industrial chairs and industry-university labs</p>
ITM5 - Mainstreaming comprehensive Open Science practices	<p>With this project we will build a common framework for a comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices. Adhering to Open Science, our universities will embark a complex and multi-dimensional process of transition, different for every university (depending of the local context in the process and also for individual researchers to move from traditional models and practices to new systems and values, and to produce a cultural change. This parallel action will cross all the actors and will be a key element of the new R&I joint actions and structures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OS Methodological Toolkit with a common set of good practices - Updated OS Institutional policies and actions plans - Innovative Diagnostics OS training Hub - Common ELISA mechanisms to Incentive and reward OS Network of Open Science Ambassadors 	<p>OS Methodological Toolkit with a common set of good practices</p> <p>Updated OS Institutional policies and actions plans</p> <p>Innovative Diagnostics OS training Hub</p> <p>Common ELISA mechanisms to Incentive and reward OS Network of Open Science Ambassadors</p>	<p>OS Methodological Toolkit with a common set of good practices</p> <p>Updated OS Institutional policies and actions plans</p> <p>Innovative Diagnostics OS training Hub</p> <p>Common ELISA mechanisms to Incentive and reward OS Network of Open Science Ambassadors</p>	<p>OS Methodological Toolkit with a common set of good practices</p> <p>Updated OS Institutional policies and actions plans</p> <p>Innovative Diagnostics OS training Hub</p> <p>Common ELISA mechanisms to Incentive and reward OS Network of Open Science Ambassadors</p>	<p>OS Methodological Toolkit with a common set of good practices</p> <p>Updated OS Institutional policies and actions plans</p> <p>Innovative Diagnostics OS training Hub</p> <p>Common ELISA mechanisms to Incentive and reward OS Network of Open Science Ambassadors</p>
ITM6 - Involvement of citizens, civil society and public/cities authorities in research and innovation	<p>ELISA innoCORE intends the idea of the challenges, where public authorities and organisations will be involved in the entire research and innovation process. The funding enables us to roll out innovation platforms for the dialogue with science. Citizens contribute to the innovation process by bringing in ideas in early development, prototyping and testing and product placement and implementation. Also ELISA will host open events, where the latest technological developments will be discussed. By sharing experiences, we actively aim at having an impact on the regional structures of existing business incubators and connecting the already existing infrastructure more closely across Europe.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusion of at least one active citizen focused on citizen science in any research action carried out in the context of ELISA communities - Open Call for activities fostering the participation of non-scientists in R&I activities 	<p>Inclusion of at least one active citizen focused on citizen science in any research action carried out in the context of ELISA communities</p> <p>Open Call for activities fostering the participation of non-scientists in R&I activities</p>	<p>Inclusion of at least one active citizen focused on citizen science in any research action carried out in the context of ELISA communities</p> <p>Open Call for activities fostering the participation of non-scientists in R&I activities</p>	<p>Inclusion of at least one active citizen focused on citizen science in any research action carried out in the context of ELISA communities</p> <p>Open Call for activities fostering the participation of non-scientists in R&I activities</p>	<p>Inclusion of at least one active citizen focused on citizen science in any research action carried out in the context of ELISA communities</p> <p>Open Call for activities fostering the participation of non-scientists in R&I activities</p>
ITM7 - Exploring joint structures across the European Universities on technical activities common to all "European Universities"	<p>We collaborate with other European Universities and have agreed a common response to this ITM for the 24 European Universities that were selected under the Erasmus+ work programme.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permanent exchange through a network of contact persons 	<p>Permanent exchange through a network of contact persons</p>	<p>Permanent exchange through a network of contact persons</p>	<p>Permanent exchange through a network of contact persons</p>	<p>Permanent exchange through a network of contact persons</p>

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Summary of findings of the MIRO exercise above

Institutional Transformation Module	Tangible progress as per GA (page 15)	Barriers, challenges, risks	To be done, work ahead
ITM1- Developing a common research and innovation agenda and action plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Map of strategic areas of all the members, including matching: EELISA InnoCORE - Networking Platform - Portfolio of societal needs that require scientific or technical solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strategic Research Areas mapping is done: now what? - Meaningful and long-lasting involvement of researchers: InnoCORE tools (open calls, networking platform, catalogue of infrastructures) under progress. Will these tools be sufficiently attractive and effective? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final decision and implementation of open calls. - Development and implementation of networking tool. - Other ways to engage researchers in EELISA? - Find ways to make the connection with EELISA communities.
ITM2 - Strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of at least one R&I structure (cluster, start-up, joint venture) per EELISA community, with members (individual researchers or innovators, research groups, tech companies) from at least 3 different countries per EELISA community. - Gender Equality Plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linkages between EELISA communities and InnoCORE still not defined and difficult to establish. - Keep the scientific interests of the researchers at the heart of the project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - idem (ITM1)
ITM3 - Sharing research infrastructures and other resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Portfolio of open infrastructures and equipment - Common policy for the alliance on infrastructure and equipment sharing - Roadmap for new infrastructures building and guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guarantee interoperability of EELISA IT solutions (costs?) - Keeping infrastructure catalogue updated. - Finding resources to support mobility and infrastructure sharing. - Difficulty to share without a legal framework: alignment of local procedures, avoid extra bureaucracy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the catalogue in an appealing way. - Need to reach common rules of access.
ITM4 - Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors, especially academia-business cooperation, with targeted actions aimed to put our innovations in the market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of PhD theses financed by industry and co-advised in the context of EELISA communities - Start-up initiatives - Number of industrial chairs and industry-university labs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Getting investors and industry onboard. - Long-term funding of activities (e.g. test space for prototypes). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for an external stakeholder reach out and management strategy coordinated together with EELISA and EELISA Unfolds, collaboration not discussed adequately yet. - Guarantee coordination with Unfolds: (InnoCORE inheriting successful activities) - Launch the Call for the First EELISA Prototype Contest in cooperation with the JOSEPHS

Are partners willing to allocate funds (short-, medium-, long?)

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Annex III – Data from the Questionnaire with communities and EELISA - innoCORE WP leaders

DATA FROM COMMUNITIES

Community 1

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

Main barrier for us is the classical mindset separating education from research. People and structures use to specialize in only one of these contexts.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

In every EELISA call or event, to emphasize the broad thematic field (for instance: science for generation of new materials) including in it innovations that explicitly refers to at least two of these three aspects: education/research/entrepreneurship.

Community 2:

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

Lack of time and lack of recognition of many of the activities related to EELISA.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

To carry out some EELISA Degrees that effectively integrate the development of ethical, personal, interpersonal and entrepreneurial skills.

Community 3

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

Workload, undefined external and internal organizational structure, lack of process management with and between stakeholders

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

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All EELISA institutions are both educational and research institutions. While academics train students, they also work on projects and project-related activities, so it becomes difficult for people to manage

their time at this intense pace. If there is an office that can work as a communication and process management support team, it will help develop collaborations within and outside of EELISA. If we define ourselves as EELISA European Universities, there must be a structure suitable for this. It is conceivable for each institution to have an EELISA coordination section of professionals attached to the EELISA (head) office, which is the main point of contact for responding to cooperation requests.

Community 4

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

All EELISA students must have the same opportunities; the request of specific visa is not a good starting point. Some students had to decline the participation at the excavation since the request was not timely.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

We must create a sort of EELISA student card: all the students have to be part of the same cultural system and context.

Community 5

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

On the educational side, the main barrier we observe is the lack of stable funding systems and the lack of motivation of professors to add more messes to their busy lives with little personal benefit. In the end they work voluntaristically and at a high cost in terms of personal attrition. The sustainability of communities is not resolved. The motivation associated with innovation and research is likely to offer new opportunities that are worth exploring.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

Both students and teachers have their full agendas of activities and messes. It takes a powerful motivation to get actively involved in more problems without having a clear return in the short or medium term, and those who are self-motivated, committed, and actively participate, have a high risk of burning out if they are not sufficiently accompanied and recognized

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DATA FROM EELISA & innoCORE PROJECT TEAMS

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

A. The involvement of researchers and academic staff and innovators remains difficult, as proven by the results of the I EELISA Prototype Contest or the EELISA Connect call for workshops. Despite the important efforts put in the design of these joint calls and afterwards in their dissemination, the calls got only a “mild” attention. The number of applications was not very high. It has to be noted that both were first attempts and that the quality of the applications was very good. The number of applications, although not very high, allowed for a good selection. However, it also proved that getting our academic staff, researchers and innovators on board is difficult and it is still a barrier to overcome.

The following sentence from D1.3 policy brief remains true:

“Regarding the particular case of researchers, academic staff is dealing with very heavy workloads, meeting their research and teaching responsibilities. Experienced reputed researchers usually have already well-established networks and working with peers from other universities is part of their daily routine. Getting involved in new activities and engaging with new partners is oftentimes seen as additional work with limited added value, therefore, any new initiative or tool must be carefully designed to offer them a valuable opportunity.

B. Building EELISA, and particularly its R&I dimension, is an extremely complex endeavor that requires careful intertwined with other R&I initiatives. Partners have an extremely large array of collaborations on the R&I dimension that cannot be neglected. EELISA innoCORE is part of very sensitive ecosystem. Our HEIs committed to EELISA and its linked projects to the highest level: our Rectors and vice-rectors are directly involved in the implementation of EELISA and EELISA innoCORE. EELISA is on the very top of our institutional agendas. However, and very particularly in the case of the R&I dimension, it has to be noted that our HEIs cannot focus exclusively on EELISA. Other R&I collaborations, networks and Alliances exist that our HEIs can under no circumstances neglect, disregard or, at this point, integrate within or open up for EELISA. We mean here: collaborations with other universities and research centers in certain key areas, participation in associations and networks, agreements with big industry players etc. at all levels (regional, national, European and international). The construction of EELISA European University, although being strategic for our partners, needs to coexist with other initiatives. Although this might not be considered a barrier as such, it is an aspect to be considered when we look at a future integration of strategies in the R&I.

The following sentence from D1.3 policy brief remains true:

“This process of integration and this new structure will however need to live together and respect under all circumstances the independence and autonomy of its constituent parts”.

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C. The R&I component needs to be better embedded in the work of EELISA communities. EELISA communities (<https://community.eelisa.eu/>) are working well, producing interesting and good results with a high impact in the educational dimension. Their work is focused on the educational part, but the R&I dimension still missing or less developed. Given the good work of the communities, EELISA should focus on using this existing well-functioning structure and support them in working on and integrating R&I aspects. Two EELISA Connect workshops (EELISA innoCORE) are linked with EELISA communities: EELISA Connect might be a good opportunity for supporting the R&I dimension of communities.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

A. The involvement of researchers and academic staff remains difficult. As highlighted in the policy brief, “any new initiative or tool must be carefully designed to offer them a valuable opportunity”, and any initiative put in place will require a careful post-analysis to identify what worked, what did not work and what needs to be changed to increase the involvement of researchers and innovators. It is also true that the amount of the “grants” offered was low and the collaboration offered was very punctual. Therefore, the opportunities might not have been very attractive. Still, a careful analysis is needed.

B. Building EELISA, and particularly its R&I dimension, is an extremely complex endeavour that requires careful intertwined with other R&I initiatives. No particular action or measure is applicable in this case. Building EELISA is a long-term project and the cooperation in R&I will have to co-exist with the rest of agreements and collaboration schemes our universities are involved in. As it is happening in other aspects (issuance of the first eleven “EELISA Supplements” in May 2023), cooperation in R&I is intensifying and will intensify naturally with the initiatives we are putting in place. Some very complex aspects, such as the question of the rules for opening existing infrastructure/facilities, still needs more work.

C. The R&I component needs to be better embedded in the work of EELISA communities. EELISA should focus on using the existing structures that are working well in the field of education (particularly EELISA communities) to push and integrate R&I.

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

The legislative and legal differences as well as different practices between universities create a barrier.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

I think a task force could be created to identify the institutional differences between partners. The practices of each institution should be documented to clearly see at which aspects they have different

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approaches. Which applications have flexibility in terms of legal requirements, which not should be identified, and for the comparatively more flexible ones a consensus may be provided through different institutions.

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

Considering the experience of the first Eelisa Connect Open Call, five are the barriers that I'd like to mention:

- an active participation in the R&I activities and calls mainly by actors already collaborating in the different WPs and a difficulty therefore to extend the tools and possibilities put in place to new researchers;
- a difficulty from researchers and professors' side to expand the boundaries of their already existing networks, not only because of issues of time and effort required, but also and above all of a real lack of knowledge of the research topics promoted by the various EElisa partners;
- even where there emerges a willingness to enlarge their networks, there is the objective difficulty in connecting with individual researchers or research groups collaborating on similar research topics not already included in Eelisa Communities;
- EElisa's still very driven narrative about engineering studies;
- the presence of so many tools made available for R&I that often proceed in parallel and concurrently and thus a difficulty in having a strategic level design of the various tools made available to researchers and professors.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

Possible actions to put in place:

- the possibility of extending the message and mission of the eelisa alliance and thus also of R&I activities beyond the actors who usually collaborate within WPs; Eelisa communities represent a good channel of engagement, but it is not sufficient; we need a more strategic narrative;
- the possibility of developing spaces, events, and platforms where both as individual researchers and as research groups research interests are highlighted, partner knowledge amplified, and thus collaborative R&I activities stimulated;
- the possibility to integrate the EElisa Communities and Eelisa Research Clusters into a common strategic vision;
- enhance the dissemination of communication channels both at the EEIISA level and on individual partners about whom we currently know little; how is information about R&I activities disseminated within individual partners? How can we find common dissemination and communication strategies?

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1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

1. EELISA can only offer limited resources for research and innovation and also the timeframe of the project is quite limited.
2. Oftentimes, researchers already have their existing networks and EELISA is thus of no or only of limited interest to them.
3. It is difficult to communicate all EELISA offers in all EELISA partner institutions effectively.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

1. We have to try to write additional proposals to get additional funding and to integrate the most important achievements of innoCORE into EELISA phase II.
2. We have to make attractive offers to our researchers and innovators without wasting their time.
3. We can still improve communicating the offers that EELISA has to make.

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

EELISA was built on an educational project. Its opening to research activities is a challenge as Researchers

- were not involved at the beginning (they need to catch up)
- need to know each other before setting up new collaborations (whereas for education, at least for engineering there was preexisting collaborations)

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

Appropriate long-term European funding to support initiatives within Alliances whether it is for funding actual research or networking activities.

EELISA could provide additional support to young researchers (including PhDs) to build their European professional networks

Design EELISA activities as a facilitator for institutions and researchers and not creating additional burdens (eg. Catalogue of facilities, Open Access guidance...)

1) According to your view, what are the main barriers hampering cooperation on the R&I dimensions of the EELISA European University?

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Basically, we agree with the statements provided by UPM on 18 May.

2) According to your view, what can be the main actions and measures to overcome these barriers?

Researchers inherently have a research network or connections. In such a case, it may be worthwhile to focus on complementarities, what are the locally missing competencies. Furthermore, as an incubator, EELISA should proactively encourage the meeting of researchers working in similar research fields, through central organization of workshops and invitations to researchers, thus helping the development of collaborations. (Beyond the effort that researchers should look for connections, EELISA may discover and point out potential connections).

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